

Deepening the Emmanuel Experience

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Abstract: Christmas 2020 is a historic landmark as the world is gripped by an unprecedented pandemic that has sown much unrest, distress and chaos in persons and nations. The celebration of the birth of Christ in the forlorn manger of Bethlehem reminds us that ‘God is with us,’ and he can understand our human conditions. He has tasted all the aspects of human existence and continues to be present in every person and thing. Christmas invites us to see him in those who are isolated, abandoned, depressed and lonely; we have to be responsible for our brothers and sisters. We also need to take care of the earth - ‘our common home,’ where he is present in every created reality. Our Emmanuel experience, that is the experience of God in us, in everyone and in everything, should make us kind, compassionate, and other-centered persons as was Jesus.

Keywords: *Fratelli Tutti*, Hyper-Individualism, Migrants and Refugees, Common Home, Emmanuel Experience, Listening, Neighbour.

On October 3, 2020, the eve of the feast of St. Francis of Assisi, after celebrating Mass at his tomb in Assisi, Pope Francis signed his new encyclical *Fratelli Tutti*, on fraternity and social friendship. This insightful and challenging document reveals a profound understanding of the contemporary society. In it, he presents a rundown of what he has been saying and doing during the past six years of his papacy and of course what he would want us, Christians and all people of good will, to be doing.

Although the world is still in the grip of the COVID-19 pandemic that has been afflicting millions of people, spreading fear everywhere, we hopefully look forward to Christmas, the birthday of Jesus Christ. We acknowledge that God loved us to the extent of giving his only son to be with us, becoming one of us. At the uniquely historical Christmas 2020, our task would be ‘to take a stand against hyper individualism’ which also is a grave ‘social pandemic.’ Let us now consider some of the areas that could be considered as our priorities at Christmas.

Seeking Out Jesus, a Migrant and a Refugee

A contemplation of the forlorn manger and the little babe wrapped in swaddling clothes, makes us realize that Jesus, even as a child, had to experience the pain and rejection of being a migrant, a refugee. The circumstances of his time demanded that he left his native place and travelled to Bethlehem. Luke tells us that he was unwelcome and met with refusal at every door they knocked at. Finally, Mary gave birth to Jesus in a cattle shelter. It is said, at his birth, the angels sang and announced the “news of great joy” to the shepherds (Lk. 2: 8-14). But practically for all purposes, the little town of Bethlehem and the world at large, slept over that great birth.

Bethlehem was not going to be his lasting residence either. He, with his parents, had to flee to Egypt to escape the rage of King Herod. That was an experience of total insecurity. Native place and home were far away realities for them and the far away land of Egypt was 'home' to them until they could return to Judea.

This plight of the Holy Family immediately brings to our mind the many migrants and refugees who either to earn a livelihood, or to find better prospects, flee their native place and homes. But due to the stringent measures and nationwide shutdown to prevent the spread of corona virus and the stringent defensive measures, they found themselves caught between the devil and deep sea. Their homeward exodus was a painful ordeal not only for them but also for every sensitive Indian. We can hardly forget the pathetic sight of their miserable journey walking long distances in the sun and rain, the most unfortunate ones getting crushed under an unannounced train.

Those abroad also faced very hoarse realities at the spread of the virus. Many of them have returned to their homes after much struggle but are left without the necessary means of living. A number of them also succumbed to the illness, leaving their dependents in total darkness.

Jesus identifies himself with these migrants, refugees and their families. We are invited at this Christmas to reach out to them as did the 'Good Samaritan.' Each parish could make their Christmas meaningful by welcoming the migrant/ displaced/ stranded/ distressed people in their territory, as they would receive Jesus. They are Christ for us today, waiting to be welcomed in.

Pope Francis couldn't say it better, "We can start from below and, case by case, act at the most concrete and local levels, and then expand to the farthest reaches of our countries and our world, with the same care and concern that the Samaritan showed for each of the

wounded man's injuries. For Christians, the words of Jesus have an even deeper meaning. They compel us to recognize Christ himself in each of our abandoned or excluded brothers and sisters (*Fratelli Tutti*, No 78).

Solidarity with Creation, Care for 'Our Common Home'

The incarnate Christ was born in a manger, amidst animals, straw, grass and rocks – yes, in the heart of Nature. There is an ecological aspect associated with his birth. He befriended not only humans but also all of creation. He created harmony between him and the reality around him. When we learn to live in harmony with all created realities, Christmas acquires its fullest significance.

St. Francis of Assisi, 'the saint of fraternal love, simplicity and joy,' was one who was most absorbed by this ecological facet of Christ's incarnation. His representation of the Nativity of Christ through cribs was but one of the expressions of this experience but he went further. The contemplation of the incarnate Christ enabled him to befriend all created things. For that reason, he considered them – people, birds and animals, plants, rivers and seas, as his brothers and sisters; brother fox, brother sun, sister moon, sister bird, sister stream and even sister death!

In Jesus, God united himself to the created world and all creation assumed a new dimension in the incarnate God who became part of our existence. This ecological perspective that Christ is in all creation is to be developed in our parishes to help our people to see and experience God in all realities of life and care for the earth, 'our common home.' Pope Francis' encyclical *Laudato Si'*, is a sure and practical guide in this endeavour. An attempt for a serious study of this document at parish and community would be of great benefit, as it speaks volumes about our predicament today as well.

Grow in the ‘Emmanuel’ Experience

Both the above aspects – care for the needy brethren and care for ‘our common home,’ are inseparably related to the fact that the Son of God became for us “Emmanuel,” God with us. Just like us humans, creation also is the spark of God, and all created realities claim, ‘God is with us.’ They too have God’s signature laid on them. Jesus is the ‘God with us’ for us humans and for every created existence. Every spark of life therefore, proclaims the presence of Christ in them. Teilhard de Chardin underlines this truth; “Christ is to incorporate all things in himself and then to return to the bosom of the Father with the world gathered up in himself” (*Teilhard de Chardin*, 264). Our joy at Christmas 2020 shall be replenished, by consciously growing in the ‘Emmanuel – God with us’ experience; experience his closeness by encountering Him in every person, in all creation.

From such an experience we will be empowered to encounter humanity in its present conditions, “Communicating, encountering people as and where they are (Theme for the World Day of Communications, 2021). Just as Jesus became fully human in order that through Him God could encounter you and me where we are, we also are invited to encounter humanity in its present conditions. For this, the Pope recommends the wise use of media in all their forms.

Communicating as did God, gives life. It is self-giving. It costs to sit down and listen to others. *FT* highlights this aspect: “At times, the frantic pace of the modern world prevents us from listening attentively to what another person is saying. Halfway through, we interrupt the other and want to contradict what s/he has not even finished saying.” Saint Francis “heard the voice of God, he heard the voice of the poor, he heard the voice of the infirm and he heard the voice of nature. He made of it a way of life (*No.48*). At this

Christmas, this seed that Saint Francis planted needs to be grown in our hearts, in our parishes and communities.

Our family members are our closest ‘neighbours’ to be loved and cared for. The COVID situation necessarily invites us to nurture and focus on our families – ‘domestic churches.’ Family has to acquire the pivotal place in our celebrations, making even the smallest gesture of love and care, a step towards better relatedness and joy.

Conclusion

As we await the Prince of peace, our focus shall turn towards harmony within us and in the world. The deep longing and choices towards true peace and reconciliation are to become the thrust of our Advent prayer and meditation.

May the star of Bethlehem lead our way to truly human relatedness, genuine compassion for all, harmony with God and his creation. Let the joy and peace of the newborn King fuel our journey of hope.

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